

Supporting Information:

Ring Opening Dynamics of the Cyclopropyl Radical and Cation: The Transition State Nature of the Cyclopropyl Cation

Nadav Genossar,^{†,‡} P. Bryan Changala,[¶] Bérenger Gans,[§] Jean-Christophe Loison,^{||} Sebastian Hartweg,^{⊥,△} Marie-Aline Martin-Drumel,[§] Gustavo A. Garcia,[⊥] John F. Stanton,[#] Branko Ruscic,[@] and Joshua H. Baraban^{*,†}

[†]*Department of Chemistry, Ben-Gurion University of the Negev, Beer Sheva 841051, Israel*

[‡]*Israel Atomic Energy Commission, P.O. Box 7061, Tel Aviv 61070, Israel*

[¶]*Center for Astrophysics — Harvard & Smithsonian, Cambridge, Massachusetts 02138, United States*

[§]*Université Paris-Saclay, CNRS, Institut des Sciences Moléculaires d'Orsay, 91405 Orsay, France*

^{||}*Université Bordeaux, CNRS, Bordeaux INP, ISM, UMR 5255, F-33400 Talence, France*
[⊥]*Synchrotron Soleil, L'Orme des Merisiers, St. Aubin BP48, F-91192 Gif sur Yvette, France*

[#]*Quantum Theory Project, Departments of Chemistry and Physics, University of Florida, Gainesville, Florida 32611 (USA)*

[@]*Chemical Sciences and Engineering Division, Argonne National Laboratory, Lemont, Illinois 60439, United States*

[△]*Present Address: Physikalisches Institut, Universität Freiburg, 79104 Freiburg, Germany*

E-mail: jbaraban@bgu.ac.il

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Calculated geometries, harmonic frequencies, and relevant force fields for the spectral simulation are supplied in an Excel file.

1 The Photoelectron Spectrum

Figure S1: The measured ms-TPES, the photoelectron spectra extracted from our data at constant photon energies of 9.0 and 9.5 eV and the spectrum of Dyke *et al.* taken at 21.22 eV.^{S1}

The newly measured mass-selected threshold photoelectron spectrum (ms-TPES), along

with constant photon energy photoelectron spectra extracted from our data at photon energies of 9.0 and 9.5 eV, are compared in Fig. S1 to the photoelectron spectrum measured by Dyke *et al.*^{S1} In all curves, the energy axis corresponds to the ion energy – meaning the energy of the photon minus the energy of the electron – and so the key difference between the photoelectron spectra and the ms-TPES is whether the photon or the electron energy is (approximately) constant. The full (rotated) photoelectron matrix is displayed in Fig. SS1 (a), where the key differences between extraction of ms-TPES *vs.* photoelectron spectra are shown. Fig. SS1 (b) zooms in on the region of the allyl peaks, where it is evident that the allyl features are obscured and effectively vanish above electron energies of 0.1 eV. The same phenomenon is observed in Fig. S1 – the allyl ms-TPES peaks around 8.2 eV are not discernible in the photoelectron spectra. Moreover, it is observed that while the possible vibrational structure discussed by Dyke *et al.* appears in our photoelectron spectra, it is absent from the ms-TPES data. We believe that the ms-TPES data is more straightforward to interpret due to these complications in the photoelectron spectra. The interpretation of the photoelectron spectrum put forward by Dyke *et al.*, including their proposed adiabatic ionization energy (IE) for cyclopropyl, was also predicated on prevailing theoretical calculations at the time, which predicted the cyclic cation to be a local minimum.

A brief discussion of the allyl radical signal is also warranted here. It does not arise from a propene impurity in the propane ring sample because no propene signal appears (IE = 9.73 eV so 0.13 eV below the IE of cyclopropane) at m/z 42 in the F-free spectrum. Furthermore, the reaction $F + c\text{-C}_3\text{H}_6 \rightarrow \text{HF} + c\text{-C}_3\text{H}_5$ is calculated (at the M06-2X/AVTZ level) to be exothermic by 117 kJ/mol and the TS for the isomerization of $c\text{-C}_3\text{H}_5$ to the allyl radical (CH_2CHCH_2) is 113 kJ/mol above the energy of the cyclopropyl radical (at the same level of theory for the purposes of comparison; see the main text for more accurate values). Since the exothermicity is most likely distributed over all degrees of freedom, especially in the HF vibration compared to $F + \text{CH}_4$ or C_2H_6 ,^{S2,S3} the isomerization of $c\text{-C}_3\text{H}_5$ into CH_2CHCH_2 is unlikely to explain the observed signal. Since we are working with a relatively

high concentration of atomic fluorine, and thus relatively high concentration of $c\text{-C}_3\text{H}_5$, the $c\text{-C}_3\text{H}_5 + c\text{-C}_3\text{H}_5$ reaction is probably non-negligible. By comparison to the allyl + allyl reaction, this reaction produces likely mainly $\text{C}_3\text{H}_4 + \text{propene}$ and perhaps is the route of production of allyl radicals in our experiment through the $\text{F} + \text{propene}$ reaction. Supporting evidence for this hypothesis is the appearance of propene at m/z 42 in the presence of atomic fluorine and cyclopropane. Since neither this side reaction nor the presence of allyl peaks interferes with the present study, we have not pursued this avenue further.

Figure S1: (a) The rotated photoelectron matrix. The colormap displays normalized photoelectron counts in arbitrary units. The horizontal arrow corresponds to the evaluation of the ms-TPES with $E_{\text{Electron}} \approx 0$ and the diagonal arrow corresponds to the evaluation of the photoelectron spectra with constant E_{Photon} . (b) A zoomed in view on the energies of the allyl peaks (8.1-8.2 eV). Note how the allyl peaks, which are clearly evident in low electron energies, essentially vanish above electron energies of 0.1 eV.

2 Reduced Dimensionality Potential Energy Surfaces

Three-dimensional reduced dimensionality potential energy surfaces (PESs) were calculated for both the radical and cation ground electronic states, using frozen-core (FC)-EOMIP-CCSD/ANO0 and (FC)-CCSD(T)/ANO1 respectively. The surface for the radical made use of equation of motion techniques in order to use a more stable Hartree-Fock reference, *i.e.* the closed-shell anion reference. The coordinates that were scanned correspond to the

rotor angles of the two terminal CH₂ groups (ϕ_1 and ϕ_2), and to the C–C–C angle (α_c). The rest of the coordinates were optimized. Examples of various cuts of the PESs are given in Fig. S2. Propagator based simulations using the reduced dimensionality PESs were attempted as well, however these resulting spectra matched poorly to the experimental ms-TPES, no doubt due to the neglect of the rest of the degrees of freedom, particularly the α C–H out of plane angle. One dimensional paths (see Figs. 3 and 4 of the main text) connecting the cyclic and allyl geometries were extracted from both PESs, retaining either C_s or C_2 symmetry, corresponding to the disrotatory or the conrotatory ring-opening paths respectively. The paths were extracted using a gradient descent approach, starting from the relevant saddle point in between the two geometries on the corresponding sub-surfaces (or from the cyclic geometry, in the case of the cation disrotatory path).

3 Thermochemical results

The results of the thermochemical calculations, along with a comparison of the resulting enthalpies of formation (ΔH_f°) to the values from versions 1.128 and 1.130 of the Active Thermochemical Tables (ATcT),^{S4} are given in Table S1. The latter version of the ATcT includes contributions from our calculations, while the former does not. Details on the calculations of the various HEAT contributions are given in Ref. S5. The most significant refinement upon inclusion of our calculations in the ATcT is of the cyclopropyl cation ΔH_f° . In the computational results, for the vertically excited cation, a zero-point energy (ZPE) is not reported as it is not a stationary point; therefore a ΔH_f° value for it is also not given, and the reported total energy value for it does not include any ZPE contribution. All of our results are within less than 1 kJ/mol from the values of version 1.128, and almost all of them are within the reported uncertainty. The calculated adiabatic ionization energies for the allyl and cyclopropyl radicals are 8.139 eV and 8.269 eV respectively.

Table S1: Breakdown of the contributions to the HEAT-345(Q) calculations and a comparison of the calculated ΔH_f° to values from versions 1.128 and 1.130 of the ATcT (with and without the contributions from this work, respectively). All values are given in Hartrees, except for the bottom three rows (ΔH_f° values), which are given in kJ/mol and are at 0 K.

	Allyl radical	Cyclic radical	Allyl cation	Cyclic cation	Vertical cation	Cyclopropane
SCF $_\infty$	-116.521286	-116.466309	-116.243255	-116.182064	-116.159469	-117.110744
$E_{\text{corr},\infty}$	-0.734840	-0.744332	-0.716371	-0.721594	-0.727145	-0.785482
T-(T) $_\infty$	-0.001037	-0.000234	-0.000518	-0.000471	-0.000452	0.000058
(Q)-T	-0.000922	-0.000818	-0.001026	-0.000818	-0.001011	-0.000865
DBOC	0.006162	0.006099	0.006274	0.006232	0.006267	0.006544
Darwin	-0.048075	-0.047973	-0.048169	-0.048076	-0.048071	-0.047945
ZPE	0.065139	0.066079	0.067344	0.063173		0.080341
Total energy	-117.234859	-117.187488	-116.935721	-116.883617	-116.929881	-117.858092
Elements energy	-116.078848	-116.078848	-116.078848	-116.078848		-116.578605
ΔH_f°	179.22	303.59	964.61	1101.40		71.07
ATcT Version 1.128	179.95 \pm 0.38	303.95 \pm 0.68	964.50 \pm 0.38	1102.6 \pm 1.6		71.03 \pm 0.35
ATcT Version 1.130	179.87 \pm 0.33	303.87 \pm 0.49	964.43 \pm 0.33	1101.54 \pm 0.74		71.03 \pm 0.32

4 Density of States Calculations

The construction of the one and two dimensional densities of states (*i.e.* $\rho(E)$ and $\rho(E, x)$, respectively) was performed as follows. First, the one-dimensional Schrödinger equations for the considered potentials were solved, using a discrete variable representation (DVR) approach.^{S6} For the model potential, $[-\infty, \infty]$ boundary conditions were applied (although the use of finite boundary conditions had no apparent influence), and a mass of 1 m_e was used. For the potential representing the cyclopropyl cation disrotatory mode, periodic $[0, 2\pi]$ conditions were applied, a mass of four hydrogen atoms was used, and the radius of rotation was estimated from the distance between the two H atoms at each terminal CH₂ group (divided by 2). This picture is of course quantitatively inaccurate, but the qualitative conclusions drawn from it should not change significantly in a more elaborate treatment. After solving the one-dimensional Schrödinger equations, the energy spectra were binned, the number of states in each bin was counted and divided by the bin width, and finally smoothed by a Gaussian filter, to yield $\rho(E)$. Similarly, for the construction of $\rho(E, x)$, the (E, x) space

was binned, and for each bin the absolute square of the wavefunctions of the states that fall within the energy of the bin was integrated between the x boundaries of the bin, and finally divided by the bin size. Similarly, a two dimensional Gaussian filter was applied to smooth the results. An illustration of this processes is shown in Fig S3.

Figure S2: Various cuts of the 3D PESs calculated for the radical and the cation. (a) and (b): disrotatory C_s symmetry cuts for the radical and the cation respectively; (c) and (d): constant $\alpha_c = 85^\circ$ cuts for the cation. Note the saddle point near the cation cyclic geometry ($\phi_{\text{dis}} = 90^\circ$, $\alpha_c \approx 60^\circ$) in (b). The peaks in (c) and (d) are conical intersections associated with crossings of electronic states in the forbidden conrotatory path for the cation and in both paths for the radical. The double-well potential of the radical can be seen in (c).

Figure S3: (a) A zoomed in view of the wavefunctions of the cyclopropyl cation disrotatory path potential. The z -axis is probability density. (b) The corresponding $\rho(E, x)$ (shown by the colormap), obtained by binning the space, summing the probability density in each bin and smoothing the results.

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